

Approaches to teaching grammar at level B1

Scientific degree: Assistant

Dauletnazarova Sarbinaz Pranadinovna

Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh.

Faculty of Foreign Languages

Annotation. *The article examines approaches to teaching grammar at level B1 of the English language. The context-based approach, the communicative approach, and the use of interactive teaching methods are discussed. The importance of taking into account the individual characteristics of students for effective teaching of grammar at this level is emphasized.*

Key words: *learning, grammar, level B1, English language, context-oriented approach, communicative approach, interactive teaching methods, individual characteristics, effectiveness.*

Level B1 English proficiency is an important milestone in language development as it provides basic communicative competence. Possession of this level implies the ability to understand basic grammatical structures and use them in everyday communication. For example, a student at level B1 can explain an opinion, ask a question, or talk about a past experience using simple sentences and general grammar rules.

However, teaching grammar at B1 level can be challenging as it requires a balance between theory and practice. Students at this level already have a basic understanding of grammar, but they need to deepen and broaden their knowledge to become more fluent and confident in their use of the language. Therefore, it is

important that the training is varied and includes both an explanation of new grammatical concepts and practical exercises to reinforce the material.

In addition, when teaching grammar at level B1, it is important to take into account the individual characteristics of students. Some may take longer to grasp certain concepts, while others may learn the material more quickly. Therefore, teachers must be prepared to adapt their teaching methods and provide additional support to those students who need it.

One effective approach to teaching grammar at B1 level is the context-based approach. It is based on the study of grammatical rules in specific communication situations, which helps students better understand and remember the rules by applying them in practice. For example, learning materials may include dialogues or texts that use target grammatical structures, making learning more visual and accessible.

The context-based approach promotes a deeper understanding of grammatical rules and their application in real-life communication situations. This approach also helps students develop skills in using grammar independently in speech, which is an important aspect in achieving communicative competence.

In addition, the context-based approach helps students remember grammar rules more effectively because they see them applied in real-life situations. This makes learning more interesting and motivating, which, in turn, contributes to more successful mastery of grammar at level B1.

Another effective approach to teaching grammar at B1 level is the communicative approach. The main goal of this approach is to develop students' ability to communicate in English. Within the communicative approach, grammar is seen as a means to achieve a communicative goal. Students learn grammar by

applying it directly in various communicative situations, which contributes to a deeper understanding of the material.

The communicative approach emphasizes the practical use of language in real life situations. Students learn not only grammatical rules, but also how to apply them correctly when communicating with native speakers or other students. This approach promotes the development of real-world English communication skills and helps students become more confident and flexible in their use of the language.

In addition, the communicative approach encourages students to participate more actively in lessons and increases their motivation to learn English. Students see concrete results of their learning because they can immediately apply the learned grammatical structures in conversational practice. This creates a favorable environment for effective mastery of grammar at level B1.

Another effective approach to teaching grammar at level B1 is to use interactive teaching methods. This includes games, role-playing, group exercises and other forms of active activities. These methods not only make learning more fun, but also encourage active practice and consolidation of grammar skills.

Interactive teaching methods help students learn grammar better because they are involved in the learning process and can apply what they learn in practice. For example, as part of game exercises, students can use grammatical structures to complete tasks, which contributes to deeper memorization of the material.

In addition, the use of interactive teaching methods helps develop students' communication skills. During games and group exercises, they are forced to communicate in English, which helps them overcome the language barrier and become more confident in using the language in real situations.

In conclusion, we can summarize the main ideas of the article, emphasize the importance of choosing approaches to teaching grammar at level B1, and offer recommendations for teachers and students. Teaching grammar at B1 level plays a

key role in developing students' basic communication skills. The choice of teaching approaches must take into account both the theoretical principles of effective teaching and a practical orientation to the needs of students. A context-based approach, a communicative approach and the use of interactive methods can make teaching grammar more effective and interesting. It is important for teachers to be flexible in their choice of teaching methods, taking into account the individual characteristics of students and their learning styles. Students should actively participate in the learning process, strive to use the learned grammar in practical situations and not be afraid to make mistakes, as this is part of the learning process. Openness to new approaches and continuous development of both teachers and students play an important role in achieving success in teaching grammar at B1 level.

References:

1. Murphy, R. English Grammar in Use. Cambridge University Press, 2019.
2. Scrivener, J. Learning Teaching: The Essential Guide to English Language Teaching. Macmillan Education, 2011.
3. Thornbury, S. How to Teach Grammar. Pearson Longman, 2010.
4. Carter, R., McCarthy, M. Cambridge Grammar of English: A Comprehensive Guide. Cambridge University Press, 2006.
5. Harmer, J. The Practice of English Language Teaching. Pearson Longman, 2015.
6. Swan, M. Practical English Usage. Oxford University Press, 2016.
7. Hewings, M. Advanced Grammar in Use. Cambridge University Press, 2013.
8. Fuchs, M., Bonner, M. Grammar and Vocabulary for First Certificate. Longman, 2005.
9. Alexander, L. Longman English Grammar Practice. Longman, 1999.
10. Evans, V., Dooley, J. Upstream Intermediate B2. Workbook. Express Publishing, 2008.

